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Alcohol is not the Water of Life, but the Poison of Death!

New medical perspectives on alcoholism in Portugal,
c. 1880-1920

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José Malhoa, *Festejando o São Martinho ou os Bispos*, 1907. Museu José Malhoa, Caldas da Rainha.

Title: Alcohol is not the Water of Life, but the Poison of Death! New medical perspectives on alcoholism in Portugal, c. 1880-1920

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Abstract: At the turn of the twentieth century, alcohol consumption in Portugal was deeply rooted in popular culture. As wine production was one of the country's principal economic activities, particularly in the Douro and Alentejo regions, alcoholic beverages were widely available and enjoyed by all social classes. While wine remained the beverage of choice in village taverns and inns—the quintessential spaces of social interaction—in urban centres the consumption of beer and distilled spirits increased among the working classes. This shift in patterns of alcohol consumption contributed to the worsening of a social and public health problem that had already raised concerns among the Portuguese medical community: alcoholism. This paper examines changing perceptions of alcoholism as reflected in the work of young physicians trained at the Porto Medical-Surgical School. Through an analysis of their inaugural dissertations, it seeks to highlight emerging understandings that recognized alcoholism as a disease

requiring medical treatment rather than a moral failing or a mere vice. Addressing the causes, physiological and psychological effects, and broader consequences of alcoholism, these studies attest to the efforts of a new generation of physicians to gain a better understanding of the condition and, subsequently, to identify the most effective therapeutic approaches for its treatment.

Keywords: Alcoholism; History of Medicine; Medicalization; Public Health; Porto.